

Studies on the Dependence of Optical Activity on Chemical Constitution. Part VII. Stereoisomeric Aryl Derivatives of Imino- and Bisimino-Camphor and their Absorptive Spectra.

BY

BAWA KARTAR SINGH

AND

RAGHUNATH RAI.

Stereoisomerism of the Hantzsch-Werner type in hydrazones, semicarbazones and phenylcarbamyhydrazones of camphorquinone has been definitely established (Forster and Zimmerli, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2156), and their α and β forms are regarded as anti- and syn-carbonylic respectively :

Iminocamphor and its aryl derivatives which contain an azethenoid group should also be capable of existing in two stereoisomeric forms (I) and (II) :

The difficulty of eliminating structural isomerism in the case of the hydrazones, semicarbazones, etc., alluded

If this view is correct, then on reduction, (III), (IV) and (V) should each furnish the same bisaminocamphor derivative* (VI):

In conformity with this view it was found (*loc. cit.*) that *p:p'*-diphenylenebisamino-camphor was produced by the reduction of both the forms. This result disposes of structural isomerism of any kind, and, in conjunction with experiments on the mutual interconversion of the two forms of 4-hydroxy- α -naphthyliminocamphor by the action of solvents and heat, appears to us to establish incontestably that stereoisomerism of the Hantzsch-Werner type exists.

There is no chemical method available by which the configurations of these isomers may be allocated. The only point of attack by chemical means is the carbonyl group in the β -position of the *camphane* molecule, but its indifferent reactivity, which is familiar, does not lend itself to chemical transformations. It was, therefore, thought desirable to determine the absorption spectra of these and other similarly constituted compounds with a view to correlate them with their optical rotatory power. It is well known that unsaturation increases general

*As two new carbon atoms (marked with an asterisk) are rendered asymmetric, the optically active compounds having the configurations (III), (IV) and (V) can each yield theoretically on reduction the same three stereochemical isomers $\alpha\alpha$, $\beta\beta$, $\alpha\beta$, represented by the structural formula (VI). In practice, however, only one and the same of these isomers was produced from both the forms.

absorption, and that among the unsaturated compounds the *trans*- or *anti*- variety is more absorptive than the *cis*- or *syn*- (Stewart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 199; compare also Magini, *Atti R. Accad. Lincei.* 1903, (V), 12, ii, 29; *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1904, 2, 410). A relation between absorptive and optical rotatory power of unsaturated compounds which has been developed by Stewart (*loc. cit.*) into the rule "greater absorption, greater rotation" may be expanded into the generalisation that the *trans* or *anti* variety has greater rotation and greater absorption than the *cis* or *syn*. It was therefore hoped that as a result of the correlation of the optical rotatory power and absorption spectra of these isomers, their stereochemical configurations may be deduced. Though the attempt cannot be said to be entirely successful, some interesting results have emerged from this work.

In Fig. I, the absorption spectra curves of the two forms of *p:p'*-diphenylene- and *o:o'*-ditolylene-bisimino-camphor, together with those of the *o:o'*-dimethoxydiphenylene derivative in chloroform solution are given. It is seen that these compounds exhibit general absorption. The data with regard to these compounds (*loc. cit.*) may be conveniently summarised here :

TABLE I.

p:p'-Diphenylenebisiminocamphor.

Colour.	m.p.	Solubility.	$[M]_D$	Absorption.
1. Golden-brown	274°	more	5433°(CHCl ₃)	more
2. Green	276°	less	5472 ,,	less

Fig. 1

- X—p: *p*-DIPHENYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR (GREEN VARIETY).
- p: *p*-DIPHENYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR (RED VARIETY).
- p: *p*-DITOLYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR (GREEN VARIETY).
- p: *p*-DITOLYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR (GOLDEN YELLOW VAR:).
- p: *p*-DIMETHOXY-DIPHENYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR.
- p—p: *p*-DIMETHOXY-DIPHENYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR.

(AFTER THE SOLUTION HAD BEEN KEPT FOR A WEEK).

o:o'-Ditolylenebisiminocamphor.

Colour	m.p.	Solubility	[M] _D	Absorption
1. Yellow	198-199°	more	4007°(CHCl ₃) 3462 (CH ₃ OH)	more
2. Green	200-201°	less	3929 (CHCl ₃) 3274 (CH ₃ OH)	less

The yellow variety of *o:o'*-ditolylenebisiminocamphor which is more absorptive than the green variety (as its curve lies at lower frequencies) possesses higher rotatory power, and this is in harmony with Stewart's rule (*loc. cit.*) It may, therefore, be represented by *trans* or *anti* configuration (III). The case is, however, different with *p:p'*-diphenylenebisiminocamphor where the more absorptive form has lower rotatory power. It is, however, to be noticed that the difference in the rotatory powers of the two forms, in this case, is very small.

The application of the relation between optical rotatory power and configuration, as deduced from a study of the hydrazones, semicarbazones and phenylcarbonyl hydrazones of Forster and Zimmerli (*loc. cit.*) leads to the same result. The α -derivatives which are regarded as *anti*-carbonylic have higher molecular rotation. In other words, the higher rotatory power is associated with *anti* or *trans*-configuration. The *o:o'*-ditolylene derivative which has higher rotatory power would be regarded as *anti*, and should, therefore, be more absorptive. This is found to be the case. The *p:p'*-diphenylene derivative which has higher rotatory power would likewise be represented by *anti* configuration. It should, therefore, be more absorptive but it is less. The uncertainty caused by the existence of a third configuration in the bisiminocamphor derivatives is not to be overlooked, and we are not sure which two pairs are being compared. This may

explain the anomalous results in the case of the diphenylene derivatives.

In Fig. II, the absorptive spectra curves of six compounds in chloroform solution are plotted. These compounds, which naturally fall in two series, also exhibit general absorption. The relation between rotatory power, absorptive power, and unsaturation is brought out very clearly by counting the number of double linkings in the structural formulae of these compounds (Tables II and III), and comparing the molecular rotatory powers and absorption spectra curves in chloroform :

TABLE II.

7 double linkings,
but conjugation broken
at dotted line.

7-double linkings,
conjugation complete.

9-double linkings,
conjugation complete.

FIG. II

- PHENYL-IMINOCAMPHOR.
- - - *m*-PHENYL-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR.
- . - *p*-PHENYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR.
- . . . α -NAPHTHYL-IMINOCAMPHOR.
- · - · α -NAPHTHOL-IMINOCAMPHOR (OR, *p*-HYDROXY- α -NAPHTHYL-IMINOCAMPHOR.)
- X - 1:4-NAPHTHYLENE-BIS-IMINOCAMPHOR.

TABLE III.

Phenyliminocamphor.	C_8H_{14}	1750°
	5 double linkings.	
α -Naphthyliminocamphor.	C_8H_{14}	1774°
	7 double linkings.	
4-Hydroxy α -naphthyliminocamphor.	C_8H_{14}	yellow form, 3991° orange form, 3948°
	7 double linkings.	

This survey shows clearly that the compounds which possess the greater number of unsaturated conjugated linkages have greater absorption as well as greater rotation. In other words, the rotatory power and the absorptive power are similarly affected by unsaturation.

4-Hydroxy- α -naphthyliminocamphor (unpublished yet) exists in two modifications, orange and yellow, which are undoubtedly stereoisomeric of the type under discussion. They, however, give an identical absorption spectrum curve (Fig. II), which is that of the equilibrium mixture of the two varieties in solution. This view receives support from observations on mutarotation in methyl alcohol; the value of $[M]_D$ for the yellow form

is 5070° (after six minutes), 4095° ($3\frac{1}{2}$ hours), and 3733° (27 hours); that for the orange variety to 3516° ($\frac{1}{2}$ hour). The values of $[M]_D$ in chloroform (Table III) are practically identical and refer to those of the equilibrium mixture of the two forms. This is confirmed by the direct transformation of the yellow forms into the orange in these solvents. The reverse change is brought about by heat.

Received July 10, 1926.

THE CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
CUTTACK.